
A New Strategy for Artificial Intelligence: Training Foundation Models Directly on Human Brain Data

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ABSTRACT

While foundation models have achieved remarkable results across a diversity of domains, they still rely on human-generated data, such as text, as a fundamental source of knowledge. However, this data is ultimately the product of human brains, the filtered projection of a deeper neural complexity. In this paper, we explore a new strategy for artificial intelligence: moving beyond surface-level statistical regularities by training foundation models directly on human brain data. We hypothesize that neuroimaging data could open a window into elements of human cognition that are not accessible through observable actions, and argue that this additional knowledge could be used, alongside classical training data, to overcome some of the current limitations of foundation models. While previous research has demonstrated the possibility to train classical machine learning or deep learning models on neural patterns, this path remains largely unexplored for high-level cognitive functions. Here, we classify the current limitations of foundation models, as well as the promising brain regions and cognitive processes that could be leveraged to address them, along four levels: perception, valuation, execution, and integration. Then, we propose two methods that could be implemented to prioritize the use of limited neuroimaging data for strategically chosen, high-value steps in foundation model training: reinforcement learning from human brain (RLHB) and chain of thought from human brain (CoTHB). We also discuss the potential implications for agents, artificial general intelligence, and artificial superintelligence, as well as the ethical, social, and technical challenges and opportunities. We argue that brain-trained foundation models could represent a realistic and effective middle ground between continuing to scale current architectures and exploring alternative, neuroscience-inspired solutions. We also note that future discoveries in cognitive and computational neuroscience could make this strategy increasingly relevant over time, as new neural signals of interest are retroactively unlocked in present neuroimaging datasets.

Keywords: foundation models, brain, neuroimaging, brain-generated data, brain-trained foundation models, reinforcement learning from human brain (RLHB), chain of thought from human brain (CoTHB)

1 INTRODUCTION

Foundation models, defined as models trained on broad data and adaptable to a wide range of downstream tasks, have rapidly emerged as the dominant paradigm in contemporary artificial intelligence (AI) (Bommasani et al., 2022). The applications of foundation models are remarkably diverse, ranging from text (Brown et al., 2020; Touvron et al., 2023), image (Ramesh et al., 2022; Alayrac et al., 2022), and video (Singer et al., 2022) generation to programming (Li et al., 2022), robotics (Ahn et al., 2022; Driess et al.,

2023), mathematics (Collins et al., 2024), and scientific research in domains such as physics (Farhadloo et al., 2025), chemistry (Méndez-Lucio et al., 2024), and biology (He et al., 2025). While these models can be trained on various data types, their most important source of knowledge is arguably the vast corpus of human-generated data, such as text and speech, which can serve as a semantic interface between different modalities (Ahn et al., 2022; Driess et al., 2023). However, this data is ultimately the product of human brains, the filtered projection of a deeper, higher-dimensional neural complexity. In this paper, we explore the possibility of moving beyond human actions such as writing and speaking, and discuss how foundation models could be trained directly on human brain data.

To formalize this idea in intuitive terms, let us introduce a simple notation. If $B(t)$ represents the brain activity of a human subject over time, and $A(t)$ the observable actions of this subject, then $A(t)$ can be considered a subset of $B(t)$, since all voluntary actions originate in the brain activity. And if $B^*(t)$ represents the available neuroimaging data for the same subject, then $B^*(t)$ can serve as an approximation of $B(t)$. This deceptively simple idea, which we could call the *generative brain principle*, has a surprisingly profound implication for foundation models, as illustrated in Figure 1: it suggests that all human-generated data could, in principle, be directly inferred from human brain activity, within the limits of the quality and availability of neuroimaging data, and of the performance of brain decoding models. To make this idea more concrete, let us consider the fact that natural language can be decoded from neural signals, with models capable of reconstructing text from imagined (Tang et al., 2023), attempted (Willett et al., 2023), or inner (Kunz et al., 2025) speech. Theoretically, this suggests that if we had access to unlimited neuroimaging data, we should be able to reconstruct every piece of text or speech ever included in the training corpus of a foundation model, up to a certain precision defined by the quality of the data and the performance of the decoding.

Practically, of course, it would make little sense to use the scarce and expensive neuroimaging data at our disposal, $B^*(t)$, for the sole purpose of reconstructing text, speech, or other observable human actions, $A(t)$. It is obviously much more efficient to rely on the human-generated data already available, which is several orders of magnitude more abundant and affordable. However, the true potential of neuroimaging data is not to infer human actions, but to reveal the generative processes of human cognition underlying these actions. Based on the discoveries in cognitive and computational neuroscience, we suggest that a diversity of neural signals could potentially be leveraged to gain a deeper understanding of the processes that determine, for example, the choice of a particular word. While neuroimaging data provides only a simplified representation of the underlying neural complexity of the human brain, it could give us access to a cognitive latent space that partially includes, but vastly exceeds, the narrow bandwidth of observable behavior. In other words, we hypothesize that $B^*(t)$ could include elements of $B(t)$ that are not included in $A(t)$, and that adding neuroimaging data to the training corpus of foundation models, alongside classical training data, could allow these models to move beyond surface-level statistical regularities, potentially overcoming some of their current limitations. Throughout this paper, expressions such as “training on human brain data” should be understood in their broadest sense, encompassing any form of learning, fine-tuning, or alignment that leverages neural signals in the training strategies of models. While a variety of specific implementations are possible, we argue that this general idea has the potential to serve as a new strategy for AI, and could represent the next frontier for improving foundation models.

This would not be the first time that new possibilities emerge at the intersection of neuroscience and AI. These two related domains share an intellectually rich and mutually beneficial history (Hassabis et al., 2017). Research on the human brain and other nervous systems has inspired the development of deep learning models such as multilayer perceptrons (Rumelhart et al., 1986), convolutional neural networks

Figure 1. Generative brain principle. *Left:* Human brain activity, $B(t)$, can be approximated by neuroimaging data, $B^*(t)$, while generating observable actions, $A(t)$. *Right:* The Venn diagram illustrates the relationship between the three sets, with the yellow area at the intersection of $B^*(t)$ and $A(t)$ representing the observable actions that can be decoded from neuroimaging data. The teal area, included in $B^*(t)$ but not in $A(t)$, represents the additional information that could be gained from incorporating neuroimaging data into foundation models. Future advances in neuroimaging technologies could gradually expand $B^*(t)$, resulting in a better approximation of $B(t)$.

(Lecun et al., 1998), and deep reinforcement learning agents (Mnih et al., 2015). In return, these models have significantly contributed to a better understanding of the human brain, by allowing researchers to decode complex neural patterns (Tang et al., 2023; Willett et al., 2023; Kunz et al., 2025). However, recent advances in training classical machine learning or deep learning models directly on human brain data open a particularly novel, and largely uncharted path, at the intersection of neuroscience and AI. It could be seen as a form of Copernican Revolution, where instead of designing models inspired by the human brain, researchers start with well-established models and guide them using neuroimaging data. Nevertheless, while foundational research has highlighted the potential of such methods (Spampinato et al., 2017; Fong et al., 2018), this path remains largely unexplored for high-level cognitive functions. Furthermore, the general implications of this approach for foundation models have, to our knowledge, never been comprehensively investigated. In this paper, our objective is to develop a theoretical foundation for this important subject, highlighting a series of brain regions and cognitive processes whose neural signals could help overcome some of the current limitations of foundation models. We also propose two methods that could be implemented to prioritize the use of limited neuroimaging data for strategically chosen,

high-value steps in foundation model training, while discussing the potential long-term implications for agents, artificial general intelligence (AGI), and artificial superintelligence (ASI).

2 FOUNDATION MODEL TRAINING DATA

Foundation models are classically trained on a diversity of data types, which we can classify as either device-generated or human-generated. We use the term *device-generated data* to refer to the signals that can be recorded without explicit human involvement or interpretation: for example, natural images, videos, sounds, chemical structures, genome sequences, or neuronal spikes. In the long term, the acquisition of such data should be primarily limited by the performance and deployment of technological devices. By contrast, we use the term *human-generated data* to refer to the signals that are intentionally generated by humans, reflecting a form of semantic meaning or knowledge: for example, text, speech, code, or mathematical formulas, as well as the labels or descriptions associated with images, videos, or sounds. In the long term, the acquisition of such data should be primarily limited by the cognitive effort of human brains, which makes it more likely to be the limiting factor in the development of future foundation models (Shumailov et al., 2024). Following our notation, human-generated data belongs to the set of observable human actions, $A(t)$, for any given subject. While large language models (LLMs) trained exclusively on human-generated data (Brown et al., 2020; Touvron et al., 2023) are already capable of extracting an impressive amount of factual (Petroni et al., 2019) and commonsense (Sap et al., 2019) knowledge, the combination of human-generated data with device-generated data has proven even more powerful, as demonstrated by the success of large multimodal models (LMMs) (Ramesh et al., 2022; Alayrac et al., 2022; Singer et al., 2022; Ahn et al., 2022; Driess et al., 2023), where human-generated data can serve as a semantic interface between different modalities of device-generated data.

To build a better understanding of the semantic gradient from device-generated data to human-generated data, let us consider the fact that some specialized foundation models are trained primarily or exclusively on recorded signals, combining for example natural videos with neuronal activity in mice (Wang et al., 2025). Even specialized AI systems, like those dedicated to the prediction of protein structure (Jumper et al., 2021) or the discovery of new crystals (Merchant et al., 2023), are occasionally considered to be foundation models, despite the fact that they are trained for a much narrower task than their general-purpose counterparts. With these particular cases at one end, we could visualize a *foundation model continuum*, as illustrated in Figure 2: a progression from specialized foundation models, relying predominantly on device-generated data; to LMMs, trained on both classes of data; to LLMs, relying predominantly on human-generated data. Interestingly, the foundation models that exhibit the highest degree of generality, as well as the closest resemblance to human cognition, seem to stand at an intermediate position in this continuum. The training data of these particular models spans the full semantic gradient, including both natural inputs of the human brain, such as visual or auditory signals, and symbolic outputs of the human brain, such as text or speech. Yet even for these models, the human brain itself remains a black box.

The foundation model continuum could be extended along another dimension: the classical series of levels of organization, where domains such as physics, chemistry, biology, and neuroscience build upon each other in a logical progression. Whereas specialized foundation models are often used to predict phenomena at the physical, chemical, or biological level, we suggest that general-purpose foundation models could be seen, with some caution, as end-to-end predictors for the neural level, since they are fundamentally trained to predict the outputs of human cognition based on its inputs. Alternatively, these models could also be seen as predictors for the cognitive level, if we distinguish cognition as a domain of its own. Either way, this function sets them apart from the specialized foundation models developed

Figure 2. Foundation model continuum. Foundation models are represented along two dimensions: the semantic gradient from predominantly device-generated data to predominantly human-generated data (x-axis), and the levels of organization (y-axis). Specialized foundation models are typically grounded in device-generated data, LMMs combine both data types, and LLMs rely primarily on human-generated data. Two empty regions highlight current constraints: the top-left corner, where it is currently difficult to imagine a foundation model of human cognition that does not significantly leverage human-generated data; and the bottom-right area, where it is equally difficult to imagine foundation models for natural sciences that do not primarily rely on device-generated data. Interestingly, a foundation model of human cognition grounded exclusively in neuroimaging data would naturally fall within the first empty region. However, we do not represent our hypothetical brain-trained foundation models there, since in the models we envision, neuroimaging data would serve as a complement, rather than a replacement, for more classical data types. The idea of fully brain-trained foundation models relying solely on neuroimaging data is intriguing, but beyond the scope of this paper.

specifically for neuroscience, which are typically not end-to-end but dedicated to the prediction of specific phenomena, such as neuronal spikes (Wang et al., 2025). Importantly, general-purpose foundation models, which will be our focus in the remainder of this paper, are not designed to emulate a particular human brain: rather, they seem to simulate an unrealistic, idealized form of human cognition, often combining considerable knowledge with a helpful attitude. Still, the possibility to formulate a request in natural language, and to receive an understandable answer that seems to be generated by a fellow human brain, is arguably the most important factor behind the ease of use and widespread adoption of LLMs and LMMs. Although seeing foundation models as end-to-end predictors for the neural level, or as predictors for the cognitive level, is admittedly an unusual perspective, it effectively highlights the oddity of considering the human brain as a black box. Paradoxically, even if LLMs and LMMs are implicitly designed to function

as an idealized form of human cognition, their training strategies never leverage the insights of actual neuroimaging data. We argue that this missing piece could partially explain some of the current limitations of foundation models, which we discuss in the next section.

3 FOUNDATION MODEL ARCHITECTURES AND LIMITATIONS

Foundation models are typically based on the transformer architecture (Vaswani et al., 2017), often combined with diffusion models (Ho et al., 2020) for specific generative tasks. Their training strategies usually follow a three-step process: large-scale pre-training (Brown et al., 2020) on a vast corpus of data to capture statistical regularities; supervised fine-tuning (Ouyang et al., 2022) on selected examples to optimize the model for its intended usage; and preference fine-tuning, typically conducted using reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF) (Christiano et al., 2017), to align the model with human values. At inference time, techniques such as chain-of-thought (CoT) prompting (Wei et al., 2023), even with very simple prompts (Kojima et al., 2022), can improve the performance of foundation models when applied to complex tasks requiring step-by-step reasoning. While the combination of these approaches has allowed researchers and engineers to develop models of extraordinary capabilities, these methods remain dependent on observable human actions, $A(t)$, with no access to the generative processes of human cognition underlying these actions. For example, RLHF relies on human ratings, while CoT is guided using examples of human reasoning. Interestingly, the reliance on surface-level statistical regularities could partially explain some of the current limitations of foundation models, which we classify here along four levels.

3.1 Perception Level

In the context of foundation models, we define *perception* as the ability to construct robust representations of sensory inputs. Although multimodality tends to improve the robustness of foundation models (Radford et al., 2021), these models remain surprisingly fragile in the way they represent perceptual information. Unlike the human brain, they are often sensitive to small perturbations or novel contexts, reducing their ability to generalize beyond their training data distribution (Hendrycks et al., 2021). One possible explanation for these fragile perceptual representations could be the fact that pre-training methods rely on human-generated data, such as the labels or descriptions associated with images, videos, or sounds, which only capture surface-level perceptual regularities and can drive the system toward superficial solutions (Geirhos et al., 2020). Strategies to mitigate this effect include adversarial training (Madry et al., 2019) and data augmentation (Hendrycks et al., 2020), with the common objective of making the models more resistant to perturbations.

3.2 Valuation Level

In the context of foundation models, we define *valuation* as the ability to align with human values. Although post-training methods such as RLHF are designed specifically for this objective, foundation models remain imperfectly aligned with human preferences. Unlike the human brain, they are often vulnerable to misalignment in novel or ambiguous contexts (Khamassi et al., 2024). One possible explanation for this imperfect value alignment could be the fact that post-training methods rely on human-generated data, such as ratings, which only capture partial valuation processes and cannot easily represent human values (Casper et al., 2023). Strategies to mitigate this effect include extensions of RLHF, such as reinforcement learning from AI feedback, to optimize the use of human-generated data (Bai et al., 2022),

as well as new approaches, such as inverse reinforcement learning, to recover the implicit reward function of foundation models (Joselowitz et al., 2025).

3.3 Execution Level

In the context of foundation models, we define *execution* as the ability to coordinate and sustain complex tasks. Although inference techniques such as CoT can improve their performance, foundation models remain limited in their reasoning and planning abilities. Unlike the human brain, they do not implement the equivalent of a robust working memory (Wang and Sun, 2025), and struggle with reasoning and planning tasks outside their training data distribution (Stechly et al., 2025). One possible explanation for this limited executive function could be the absence of mechanisms comparable to the cognitive control of the human prefrontal cortex (Russin et al., 2020), and the difficulty of approximating such control from human-generated data alone. Strategies to mitigate this effect include extensions of CoT, such as tree of thoughts (Yao et al., 2023) or graph of thoughts (Besta et al., 2024), which can expand the flexibility of foundation models at the expense of a greater computational cost.

3.4 Integration Level

In the context of foundation models, we define *integration* as the ability to form coherent concepts and generalize across novel domains. Although foundation models exhibit some elements typically associated with social cognition (Strachan et al., 2024), their conceptualization of the world and its different agents often remains superficial. Unlike the human brain, they are prone to hallucinations, generating plausible yet wrong outputs, particularly in novel or ambiguous tasks (Huang et al., 2025). One possible explanation for this shallow conceptual integration could be the absence of mechanisms comparable to the sensorimotor grounding of the human body (Xu et al., 2025a), and the difficulty of approximating such grounding from human-generated data alone. Strategies to mitigate this effect include the development of methods to detect hallucinations (Farquhar et al., 2024), as well as the growing interest in new approaches inspired by biological brains (Marshall and Barron, 2025).

Overall, these current limitations of foundation models seem to arise, at least partially, from the superficial nature of human-generated data. Strategies to overcome these limitations often involve scaling methods, such as augmenting pre-training data, expanding post-training feedback, or allocating more computational resources at inference time. However, beyond their increasing computational cost, it is unclear whether these methods will continue to yield significant progress in the long term, or whether they will reach a plateau. An alternative strategy may be the development of new foundation model architectures, perhaps inspired by biological brains. However, beyond the scientific complexity of the task, it is unclear whether such architectures would be able to extract significantly deeper regularities, assuming that they still rely on the same training corpus. Training foundation models directly on human brain data could circumvent these two difficulties, by relaxing the assumption that human-generated data is the only relevant resource for modeling human cognition. While the other strategies are focused on augmenting this resource, or adapting the entire system to better accommodate its limited supply, brain-trained foundation models would take the different and complementary approach of adding neuroimaging data to their training corpus, in order to build a deeper representation of human cognition. Exploring the feasibility of this path requires evaluating the strengths and weaknesses of the different types of neuroimaging data at our disposal, which we review in the next section.

	EEG	fMRI	MEG	ECoG	fNIRS
Spatial resolution	Low	High	Medium	Very high	Low-medium
Temporal resolution	High	Low	High	High	Medium
Brain coverage	Cortex	Whole brain	Primarily cortex	Local cortex	Superficial cortex
Invasiveness	No	No	No	Yes	No
Portability	Yes	No	No	No (medical supervision)	Yes
Cost	Low	High	High	High (surgery) / Low (recording)	Medium

Table 1. Neuroimaging techniques. Five major neuroimaging techniques (EEG, fMRI, MEG, ECoG, fNIRS) are compared across six important dimensions (spatial resolution, temporal resolution, brain coverage, invasiveness, portability, cost). Each technique comes with specific strengths and weaknesses, potentially providing complementary paths for brain-trained foundation models.

4 HUMAN BRAIN DATA

Research in cognitive and computational neuroscience relies on a variety of neuroimaging techniques, each with specific strengths and weaknesses, as summarized in Table 1. For example, electroencephalography (EEG) (Niedermeyer and Silva, 2005) measures the electrical activity of the brain, using electrodes positioned on the scalp. This technique is typically used to record the activity of cortical regions, with a low spatial resolution but a high temporal resolution. It is a relatively simple and inexpensive technique, compatible with wearable devices, and serves as the method of choice behind most commercial neural interfaces. By contrast, functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) (Logothetis, 2008) measures the metabolic activity of the brain indirectly, by detecting changes in the cerebral blood flow and oxygenation. This technique can be used to record the activity of both cortical and subcortical regions, with a high spatial resolution but a low temporal resolution. It is more complex and expensive, and requires the subject to remain immobile inside the scanner, but remains widely used in research due to its detailed and comprehensive functional maps. Importantly, these two techniques are not mutually exclusive, since they can be combined through simultaneous EEG-fMRI acquisition (Lioi et al., 2020). Furthermore, the possibility to predict fMRI activity from EEG activity could eventually be leveraged to enhance neural interfaces, and potentially achieve near-fMRI precision while retaining the affordability and wearability of EEG devices (Li et al., 2024; Donoso, 2025).

Beyond EEG and fMRI, several other neuroimaging techniques are frequently used in cognitive and computational neuroscience. Magnetoencephalography (MEG) (Baillet, 2017) measures the magnetic fields generated by the electrical activity of the brain, using highly sensitive magnetometers. This technique improves the spatial resolution over EEG while maintaining its temporal resolution, at the expense of a greater complexity and cost. Electrocorticography (ECoG) (Parvizi and Kastner, 2018) measures the electrical activity of the brain locally, using electrodes surgically implanted on the surface of the cortex. This technique provides both a high spatial resolution and a high temporal resolution, but its invasiveness currently limits its applications to medical contexts. Finally, functional near-infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS) (Ferrari and Quaresima, 2012) also offers interesting experimental possibilities, although restricted to superficial cortical regions. Like fMRI, this technique provides an indirect measure of the metabolic activity of the brain, but like EEG, it is a relatively simple and inexpensive method, compatible with wearable devices. Together, these neuroimaging techniques allow researchers to investigate human brain activity

from several complementary angles, and can often be combined, either with each other, or with additional physiological and behavioral measures (Meissner et al., 2024). The possibility to predict one neuroimaging modality from another, a process which we could call neural translation, could further expand the corpus of human brain data at our disposal, and unlock new possibilities for understanding and leveraging neural complexity.

Nevertheless, leveraging human brain data comes with specific challenges. In particular, neuroimaging data is often noisy (Liu, 2016) and distinctively individual (Finn et al., 2015), requiring methods to ensure the alignment of neural signals across subjects (Haxby et al., 2011). Furthermore, inferring a particular cognitive process from the activation of a particular brain region is not straightforward (Poldrack, 2006), although methods can be developed to evaluate and improve predictive power (Poldrack, 2011). The scarcity and heterogeneity of neuroimaging datasets can also be challenging, but these problems are increasingly mitigated by the emergence of large-scale, standardized, open repositories for neuroimaging data (Markiewicz et al., 2021). Moreover, it seems reasonable to assume that the advances in brain-computer interfaces (Willett et al., 2023) will eventually lead to a wider adoption of wearable or implantable neural technologies, resulting in a significant increase in the volume of neuroimaging data. Overall, while challenges remain, the convergence of multimodal acquisition, neural translation, open repositories, and neural interfaces is likely to make neuroimaging data increasingly compatible with the requirements of foundation model training. This could offer an unprecedented opportunity to incorporate human brain data into future foundation models, not as a mere subset of device-generated data, but as the approximation $B^*(t)$ of human brain activity $B(t)$, which is itself the superset of observable human actions $A(t)$ for any given subject. Therefore, alongside device-generated and human-generated data, we suggest that neuroimaging data could be distinguished as a new category, which we could call *brain-generated data*, in the context of foundation model training. Evaluating the potential of such data for foundation models requires identifying which specific brain regions and cognitive processes could be targeted for neural signal extraction, a question we address in the next section.

5 PROMISING BRAIN REGIONS AND COGNITIVE PROCESSES

Brain-trained foundation models could potentially leverage a diversity of neural signals, associated with different brain regions and cognitive processes, as summarized in Table 2 and illustrated in Figure 3. Interestingly, existing research on guiding machine learning or deep learning models using neuroimaging data has primarily focused on visual (Fong et al., 2018) and auditory (Freteault et al., 2025) perception, or on simple reward and error valuation (Iturrate et al., 2010). For perception, this choice was often motivated by the representational similarity between deep learning models trained for visual or auditory tasks and the corresponding sensory regions of the human brain, namely the visual cortex (Yamins et al., 2014) and the auditory cortex (Kell et al., 2018). For valuation, it was often motivated by the conceptual similarity between artificial and biological reinforcement learning (Sutton and Barto, 2018). Importantly, these foundational studies have been primarily conducted in the context of classical applications of machine learning or deep learning models, such as image recognition and audio classification. However, the transition from narrow, specialized AI systems to broader, open-ended foundation models could represent a cognitive turning point regarding the most promising neural signals to consider. As the current limitations of foundation models extend beyond perception, and require AI research to move into the realm of valuation, execution, and integration, considering higher-order neural signals could become increasingly relevant, or even necessary. Here, we classify the most promising brain regions and cognitive processes for brain-trained foundation

	Perception level	Valuation level	Execution level	Integration level
Brain regions	Visual cortex, auditory cortex, somatosensory cortex	Ventral striatum, ventromedial prefrontal cortex (vmPFC), orbitofrontal cortex (OFC), amygdala, insula	Dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (DLPFC), anterior cingulate cortex (ACC), frontopolar cortex (FPC), posterior parietal cortex (PPC), pre-supplementary motor area (pre-SMA)	Inferior frontal gyrus (IFG), angular gyrus, temporo-parietal junction (TPJ), medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC), posterior cingulate cortex (PCC)
Cognitive processes	Vision, audition, touch	Reward, value, confidence, confirmation of a rule, novelty, salience, effort, self-control, internal state	Representation of current and alternative rules, evaluation of the environment, retrieval of a rule, motivation, attention, action selection	Language production and comprehension, conceptual integration, social cognition, self-cognition, autobiographical memory
Training approach	Pattern decoding	Cognitive and computational inference	Cognitive and computational inference	Pattern decoding (language) / Cognitive and computational inference
Available research	Medium	Low	Very low	Low
Foundation model limitation	Fragile perceptual representations	Imperfect value alignment	Limited executive function	Shallow conceptual integration

Table 2. Cognitive levels. The four cognitive levels (perception, valuation, execution, integration) are compared across five important dimensions (brain regions, cognitive processes, training approach, available research, foundation model limitation). For each level, the table highlights a selection of promising brain regions and cognitive processes whose neural signals could help overcome the corresponding limitation of foundation models.

models along four levels, loosely organized by increasing degree of abstraction, and mapping to the current limitations of foundation models defined earlier.

5.1 Perception Level

Perception engages different regions of the human brain, among which the visual cortex (DiCarlo et al., 2012), the auditory cortex (Bizley and Cohen, 2013), and the somatosensory cortex (Kaas, 2008). Together, these brain regions acquire and process primary sensory information, which is then contextualized into secondary perceptual representations. Foundational research has demonstrated that fMRI data can be leveraged to improve machine learning models for an object recognition task, while also suggesting that such methods could be extended to other neuroimaging techniques, learning algorithms, and sensory modalities (Fong et al., 2018). Two other foundational studies have shown that EEG data can be used to guide deep learning models, whether for an object recognition task (Spampinato et al., 2017) or an image generation task (Palazzo et al., 2017), while similarly hinting at a possible extension of such methods beyond the visual modality (Spampinato et al., 2017). Recent research has continued to explore the opportunity to guide deep learning models for visual tasks using fMRI data (Lu and Wang, 2025; Nguyen et al., 2025; Lang et al., 2025; Zhao et al., 2025) and EEG data (Palazzo et al., 2021; Hansen et al.,

Figure 3. Cognitive levels. From left to right: Promising brain regions are represented for the perception (red), valuation (orange), execution (green), and integration (blue) levels, along with the corresponding limitation of foundation models that such neural signals could help overcome.

2025), while also extending the investigation to auditory tasks using fMRI data (Freteault et al., 2025; Moussa et al., 2025). The methods implemented in these studies are relatively variable, suggesting that a diversity of approaches can be considered to improve machine learning or deep learning models with neuroimaging data. Nevertheless, the training strategies usually involve some form of model regularization, fine-tuning, or another constraint based on neural signals, and they often leverage existing models pre-trained for visual or auditory tasks. Interestingly, rather than acquiring a new neuroimaging dataset for each experiment, it is sometimes possible to rely on synthetic data, using for example a pre-trained fMRI prediction model to generate large-scale synthetic fMRI data without additional cost (Zhao et al., 2025). These results suggest that the brain regions and cognitive processes associated with the perception level could be promising targets to overcome the fragile perceptual representations observed in foundation models, at least if such methods can be scaled. We speculate that guiding robotics models using neural signals from the somatosensory cortex may also be an interesting opportunity to explore.

5.2 Valuation Level

Valuation engages a network of cortical and subcortical regions across the human brain. Among them, the ventral striatum is associated with reward prediction (O’Doherty et al., 2004), including when the task involves planning (Daw et al., 2011). This subcortical structure serves as a motivational node even

in subliminal settings (Pessiglione et al., 2007), driving both cognitive and motor effort (Schmidt et al., 2012), as well as novelty-seeking behavior (Wittmann et al., 2008). In complex reasoning tasks, the ventral striatum also encodes the confirmation of a new rule (Donoso et al., 2014). Another important region is the ventromedial prefrontal cortex (vmPFC), which serves as a general valuation node encoding the value of the elements present in the environment (Lebreton et al., 2009), while a distinct network encodes the effort necessary to acquire such elements (Prévost et al., 2010). The valuation processes of the vmPFC are conducted independently of the category of goods, suggesting the idea of a common currency (Chib et al., 2009), and they are modulated by the degree of self-control exerted by the subject (Hare et al., 2009). The vmPFC is also engaged in more abstract valuation processes, encoding the value of the chosen action (Wunderlich et al., 2009), the value of the current rule (Kolling et al., 2012), and even the confidence associated with this rule (De Martino et al., 2013). Meanwhile, a closely related brain region, the orbitofrontal cortex (OFC), is associated with the magnitude of the rewards obtained (O’Doherty et al., 2001) and the willingness to pay in economic transactions (Plassmann et al., 2007), while being flexibly regulated according to the current state of the subject (Gottfried et al., 2003). Other important brain regions for valuation include the amygdala, which serves as an emotional node particularly involved in salience mechanisms (Phelps and LeDoux, 2005), and the insula, associated with interoception and a variety of affective processes (Craig and D, 2009). Together, these brain regions process rewards, assign a value to perceptions, actions, or rules, and motivate decision-making based on this valuation.

Although several studies have demonstrated that reward and error signals extracted from EEG data can be used to guide reinforcement learning models in robotics (Iturrate et al., 2010; Kim et al., 2017; Xu et al., 2020; Kar et al., 2022), research on using higher-level valuation processes for this objective appears to be limited. Here, we see a clear opportunity to extend the set of neural signals at our disposal, in order to leverage the full range of valuation processes of the human brain. For example, using fMRI to record simultaneously the activity of the ventral striatum, vmPFC, OFC, amygdala, and insula could provide us with a comprehensive monitoring of the valuation level. This monitoring would range from rewards (O’Doherty et al., 2001, 2004; Daw et al., 2011), to values (Plassmann et al., 2007; Lebreton et al., 2009; Chib et al., 2009; Wunderlich et al., 2009; Kolling et al., 2012), to confidence (De Martino et al., 2013), to the confirmation of a valuable rule (Donoso et al., 2014). It would also allow us to control for related variables such as novelty (Wittmann et al., 2008), salience (Phelps and LeDoux, 2005), effort (Prévost et al., 2010; Schmidt et al., 2012), self-control (Hare et al., 2009), and the internal state of the subject (Gottfried et al., 2003; Craig and D, 2009). Critically, such neural signals could extend far beyond the preference ratings currently used to align foundation models, opening a window into the generative processes underlying the expression of human values. Furthermore, at least some of these processes are automatic, requiring no voluntary action or intent (Pessiglione et al., 2007), thus offering a degree of objectivity and immediacy that distinguishes brain-generated data from human-generated data. Therefore, the brain regions and cognitive processes associated with the valuation level could be promising targets to overcome the imperfect value alignment observed in foundation models, provided that these neural signals can be effectively integrated into the training strategies of the models.

5.3 Execution Level

Execution engages a network of cortical and subcortical regions across the human brain, with the prefrontal cortex playing a central role. Among these regions, the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (DLPFC) is associated with the selection of representations in working memory (Rowe et al., 2000), and serves as a general node for the implementation of cognitive control (MacDonald et al., 2000). The architecture of this prefrontal region reflects a cascade of increasingly abstract executive processes, capable of controlling

behavior based on stimuli, context, and instructions (Koechlin et al., 2003), with each level driven by dedicated motivational mechanisms (Kouneiher et al., 2009). This organization along several levels of abstraction is consistent with the behavior of subjects with frontal damage (Badre et al., 2009), and with research on the acquisition of abstract rules (Badre et al., 2010). In complex reasoning tasks, the DLPFC also encodes the retrieval of a previous rule whose reliability continues to be monitored in working memory (Donoso et al., 2014). Another important region is the anterior cingulate cortex (ACC), which encodes the volatility of the environment (Behrens et al., 2007) and serves as a general node for evaluating the outcome of actions, integrating rewards, errors, and conflict (Alexander and Brown, 2011). In exploration-exploitation trade-off settings, the ACC represents the value of the exploratory behavior (Kolling et al., 2012). Meanwhile, another region associated with exploration, the frontopolar cortex (FPC), encodes the reliabilities of alternative rules (Boorman et al., 2009), which are continually updated based on the feedback from the environment (Boorman et al., 2011), with current and alternative rules driven by dedicated motivational mechanisms (Charron and Koechlin, 2010). Other important brain regions for execution include the posterior parietal cortex (PPC), which serves as an attentional node particularly involved in sensorimotor transformation (Andersen and Cui, 2009), and the pre-supplementary motor area (pre-SMA), associated with different types of complex action selection (Nachev et al., 2008). Together, these brain regions process the outcome of actions, assign a reliability to current and alternative rules, and implement decision-making based on stimuli, context, and instructions.

Intriguingly, despite the interest in replicating the functions of the human prefrontal cortex in AI systems (Russin et al., 2020), and although neural signals from brain regions such as the DLPFC have been used in neurofeedback studies (Godet et al., 2024), research on training models directly on these regions appears to be limited, with the exception of a recent study in which invasive recordings from the cingulate cortex, possibly including the ACC, have been used to guide a model for a decision-making task (Aquino et al., 2025). Here, as in the valuation level, we see a clear opportunity to extend the set of neural signals at our disposal, in order to leverage the full range of execution processes of the human brain. For example, using fMRI to record simultaneously the activity of the DLPFC, ACC, FPC, PPC, and pre-SMA could provide us with a comprehensive monitoring of the execution level. This monitoring would range from the representation and implementation of rules (Rowe et al., 2000; MacDonald et al., 2000; Koechlin et al., 2003; Badre et al., 2009, 2010), to the evaluation of the environment (Behrens et al., 2007; Alexander and Brown, 2011; Kolling et al., 2012), to the representation of alternative rules (Boorman et al., 2009, 2011), to the retrieval of a previous rule (Donoso et al., 2014). It would also allow us to control for related variables such as motivation (Kouneiher et al., 2009; Charron and Koechlin, 2010), attention (Andersen and Cui, 2009), and action selection (Nachev et al., 2008). Critically, such neural signals could extend far beyond the reasoning examples currently used to guide foundation models for multi-step tasks, opening a window into the generative processes underlying the decision steps of human reasoning. The concept of rule, or more appropriately task set (Sakai, 2008), defined as a configuration of cognitive processes that is actively maintained for executing a task, could provide an effective framework for interpreting neuroimaging data in this context. Therefore, the brain regions and cognitive processes associated with the execution level could be promising targets to overcome the limited executive function observed in foundation models, provided, as in the valuation level, that these neural signals can be effectively integrated into the training strategies of the models.

5.4 Integration Level

Integration engages an intricate network of cortical and subcortical regions across the human brain, with several regions playing prominent roles. Among them, the inferior frontal gyrus (IFG) serves as a general

node for language production and comprehension (Friederici, 2011), and the angular gyrus for conceptual integration (Binder et al., 2009). The temporo-parietal junction (TPJ) is particularly involved in social cognition (Carter and Huettel, 2013), while the medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC) and posterior cingulate cortex (PCC) are important nodes of the default network, supporting self-cognition and autobiographical memory (Buckner et al., 2008). Together, these brain regions allow humans to engage in symbolic thought and expression, understand the intentions of others, and reason about themselves. The complexity of these cognitive functions, and their distributed and intricate nature, make the integration level difficult to define precisely. Admittedly, we mostly use this level as a general category for higher-order cognitive functions that do not fit neatly into the perception, valuation, or execution levels. Nevertheless, a few studies have used fMRI or MEG to align language models with human semantic representations (Schwartz et al., 2019; Toneva and Wehbe, 2019), including in multilingual contexts (Negi et al., 2025), or to improve the performance of visual models (Nishida et al., 2020) or auditory models (Moussa et al., 2025) on semantic tasks. These results, along with the representational similarity observed between language models and the human brain (Schrimpf et al., 2021; Caucheteux et al., 2023), suggest that the brain regions and cognitive processes associated with the integration level could be promising targets to overcome the shallow conceptual integration observed in foundation models, at least if such methods can be scaled. Guiding models using neural signals from regions associated with social cognition or self-cognition could also be an interesting opportunity to explore, particularly in the context of AI agents. The relevance of this research direction could depend on the evolution of agentic systems, and particularly on the extent to which future agents will be expected to collaborate with each other and with human users.

Altogether, the brain regions that we identified across the perception, valuation, execution, and integration levels are associated with important cognitive processes, and could allow us to monitor the evolution of meaningful neural signals over time. Nevertheless, this list should only be considered as a starting point, since many other brain regions and cognitive processes, as well as the functional connectivity or interactions between them, could provide valuable information for foundation models. Furthermore, while we largely focused on fMRI studies, where the link between regions and processes is relatively straightforward, we must remember that other neuroimaging techniques could offer complementary insights into human brain activity at different spatial and temporal scales. Interestingly, most of the research available at the perception and integration levels follows an approach that we could call *pattern decoding*, where machine learning or deep learning models are aligned with neural representations in visual, auditory, or language regions. By contrast, the research available at the valuation level follows an approach that we could call *cognitive and computational inference*, where models are trained using neural signals reflecting specific cognitive and computational processes, such as reward and error signals extracted from EEG data. As we noted earlier, the transition to broad, open-ended foundation models could represent a cognitive turning point regarding the most promising neural signals to consider, since the current limitations of these models extend beyond the perception level. This turning point could make cognitive and computational inference increasingly important, as this approach could provide us with relevant higher-order neural signals, particularly for the valuation and execution levels.

We introduced this paper by suggesting that a diversity of neural signals could potentially be leveraged to gain a better understanding of the cognitive processes that determine, for example, the choice of a particular word. Based on the promising brain regions and cognitive processes that we identified, we can now elaborate on this example. Let us imagine that a human subject is choosing their next written or spoken word, while their brain activity is recorded using one or several neuroimaging techniques. At the valuation level, neural signals from the ventral striatum could reveal the expected reward associated with the candidate word, while the activity of the vmPFC and OFC could reflect the perceived value of the

current text or speech, or the confidence in the current verbal reasoning. Other valuation markers could account for the novelty or salience of the word, or for the effort or self-control involved. At the execution level, neural signals from the DLPFC could uncover the cognitive control mechanisms associated with the word choice, and reveal whether this decision is predominantly driven by stimuli, context, or instructions. Meanwhile, the activity of the ACC could reflect the opportunity to change the current verbal reasoning, with the FPC encoding the reliabilities of alternative words or sentences. Other execution markers could account for motivation and attention, while at the integration level, neural signals from the TPJ, mPFC, and PCC could open a window into the social or subjective dimensions behind the candidate word. Overall, whereas human-generated data is limited to observable actions, brain-generated data could give us access to values, motivations, hesitations, efforts, influences, alternatives, and other hidden variables of the cognitive latent space, in line with our hypothesis that $B^*(t)$ could include elements of $B(t)$ that are not included in $A(t)$. Nevertheless, leveraging these insights for foundation models would require dedicated methods to prioritize the use of limited neuroimaging data for strategically chosen, high-value steps in foundation model training. In the next section, we propose two such methods, and suggest that training foundation models directly on human brain data could open new horizons for agents, AGI, and ASI.

6 STRATEGIES FOR BRAIN-TRAINED FOUNDATION MODELS

Brain-trained foundation models would require dedicated methods to incorporate neural signals into their training strategies. While discoveries in cognitive and computational neuroscience have uncovered many promising brain regions and cognitive processes, existing research on guiding machine learning or deep learning models using neuroimaging data has been relatively modest in scale, and focused on a narrow set of tasks. This limited scope was most certainly necessary, considering the scarcity and cost of neuroimaging data. However, foundation models have, by contrast, emerged as powerful systems trained on large-scale data and deployed across a wide range of applications. Therefore, incorporating neural signals into their training strategies could require either scaling current efforts significantly, or prioritizing the use of limited neuroimaging data for strategically chosen, high-value steps in foundation model training. As a basis for reflection, let us consider the proposition that leveraging human brain data could be useful in two scenarios: either when its acquisition becomes less expensive than behavioral data, or when the information of interest cannot be elicited through behavior (Mineault et al., 2025). For the perception level and the linguistic tasks within the integration level, where existing research follows the pattern decoding approach, scaling current efforts could represent a reasonable path forward. Indeed, the alignment of visual, auditory, or language models with neural representations typically involves relatively large brain regions, which can increase the amount of information obtained per neuroimaging acquisition, thus lowering the cost. By contrast, for the valuation level and the execution level, where cognitive and computational inference has the potential to become increasingly relevant, prioritizing the use of neuroimaging data for strategically chosen training steps could be a strong alternative. Here, we propose two methods for this second objective, which extend, respectively, the RLHF and CoT approaches to incorporate human brain data, as illustrated in Figure 4.

6.1 Reinforcement Learning from Human Brain

The first method could be called *reinforcement learning from human brain (RLHB)*. It would be an extension of RLHF (Christiano et al., 2017) incorporating neuroimaging data, and possibly other real-time measures, for a better alignment with human values. Integrating such a method into the training strategies of foundation models seems realistic, both from a technological and a human perspective. For example, adding EEG recording to an RLHF session should only increase the cost marginally, and assuming that

Figure 4. RLHB and CoTHB. *Left:* In RLHB, a model output is presented to a subject, brain activity is recorded (here from valuation regions) as the subject evaluates the output, and neural signals are extracted to align the model. The grey arrow suggests that future outputs could be improved based on this feedback. *Right:* In CoTHB, a reasoning problem is presented to a subject, brain activity is recorded (here from execution regions) as the subject engages in reasoning, and neural signals are extracted to guide the model. The grey arrow suggests that the model could subsequently improve its ability to solve similar reasoning problems.

appropriate EEG headsets are used, it should not represent a significant problem for the comfort of the human annotators. Adding fMRI recording would be more expensive and likely result in more discomfort, since the annotators would need to remain immobile inside an fMRI scanner, but the neural signals extracted would be more comprehensive. Critically, RLHF is already an expensive and time-consuming post-training step (Xu et al., 2025b), and it is increasingly considered a bottleneck in the training strategies of foundation models (Yuan et al., 2025), suggesting that neuroimaging could be a feasible and valuable addition in this context. It is also a step requiring a significant cognitive effort from the annotators, suggesting that the relative discomfort introduced by the neuroimaging measures could be compensated if it lowers the constraints regarding the number, precision, or comprehensiveness of the ratings required. Alongside neuroimaging data, RLHB could also benefit from other real-time measures, such as eye movements, heart rate, skin conductance, or facial muscle activity, which are non-invasive and may provide valuable insights into the degree of well-being, surprise, stress, attention, conflict, or cognitive effort experienced by the annotators. Interestingly, eye tracking could be used to align neural signals with the successive segments of a foundation model output, offering the possibility to train a fine-grained reward function, in line with

current research on fine-grained human feedback (Wu et al., 2023). The ethical and social considerations, in particular the trade-off between the additional protections required for the annotators and the benefits of foundation models better aligned with human values, will be addressed in the next section.

A diversity of brain regions and cognitive processes could potentially be targeted for RLHB. At the valuation level, the monitoring of rewards, values, and confidence could effectively complement ratings as additional expressions of human preferences. The neural signals associated with novelty and salience may be useful to detect unexpected outputs, while the markers of effort, self-control, and affective processes may reveal the difficulty or ambiguity of the evaluation. These indicators could be extracted from the activity of regions such as the ventral striatum, vmPFC, OFC, amygdala, and insula. At the execution level, the monitoring of rules, alternatives, and the environment could be useful when the output is complex to evaluate, or when the annotators are asked to compare several possible outputs. The neural signals associated with motivation, attention, and action selection may provide an additional measure of their decision-making process. These indicators could be extracted from the activity of regions such as the DLPFC, ACC, FPC, PPC, and pre-SMA. Finally, at the integration level, the markers associated with conceptual integration, social cognition, and self-cognition may also be relevant, particularly for outputs with a strong intellectual, collective, or introspective dimension. These indicators could be extracted from the activity of the TPJ, mPFC, PCC, and related regions. Regarding the specific algorithms that could be used to extend RLHF into RLHB, we can think of several possibilities. Reward or value signals could be used as direct expressions of preference for training the reward function, whereas negative affective markers could serve as regularizers for penalizing some outputs. Confidence signals could be used to weight the ratings according to their reliability, whereas novelty or salience signals could be leveraged to prioritize the evaluation on unexpected or intriguing outputs. Alternatively or concurrently, the reward function could be trained to predict neural signals alongside explicit ratings, in order to increase its robustness. Furthermore, it is worth noting that the continuous nature of human brain data may provide, in some cases, the opportunity for a smoother fine-tuning compared to discrete ratings. Overall, while the specific neural signals and algorithms would likely depend on each training strategy, RLHB could emerge as a promising method for improving the alignment of foundation models with human values.

6.2 Chain of Thought from Human Brain

The second method could be called *chain of thought from human brain (CoTHB)*. It would be an extension of CoT (Wei et al., 2023) incorporating neuroimaging data, and possibly other real-time measures, for a more trustworthy emulation of human executive function. Integrating such a method into the training strategies of foundation models could require the acquisition of new neuroimaging datasets focused on human reasoning, but these investments may be justified by the strategic importance of this research direction. Critically, frameworks designed to expand the flexibility of CoT often imply a greater computational cost (Yao et al., 2023; Besta et al., 2024), and still underperform direct answering across many model scales and benchmark complexities (Zheng et al., 2025), suggesting that alternative paths such as neuroimaging could be worth considering for improving their performance. Fundamentally, CoTHB could focus on a subset of brain regions and cognitive processes particularly involved in human reasoning, using neural signals such as the reliability of the current rule, the reliabilities of alternative rules, the value of the exploratory behavior, the retrieval of a previous rule, and the confirmation of a new rule. These indicators could be extracted, respectively, from the vmPFC, FPC, ACC, DLPFC, and ventral striatum. Regarding the specific algorithms that could be used to extend CoT into CoTHB, we can think of several possibilities. The current reasoning path could be followed as long as the reliability of the current rule is high, and alternative branches could be explored when the value of the exploratory behavior

reaches a certain threshold. Alternatively or concurrently, neural signals could be used to drive the retrieval of a previous path, the confirmation of an exploratory path, or the monitoring of a specific number of alternative branches. As for RLHB, CoTHB could also benefit from other real-time measures alongside neuroimaging data. The amount of data that should be acquired to provide enough examples of human reasoning remains an open question, although it is reasonable to assume that some degree of generalization should be attainable from a limited number of carefully designed reasoning examples. As for RLHB, the ethical and social considerations will be addressed in the next section.

Compared with RLHB, using neuroimaging data in the context of CoTHB raises an interesting question. Human reasoning on complex problems can be long, often spanning several hours or even days, whereas neuroimaging data can only be acquired for shorter periods. Therefore, the insights gained from neural signals on relatively short reasoning tasks may, or may not, generalize well to the longer problems that we could expect foundation models to solve. This is less likely to be a difficulty for RLHB, where the evaluation of a foundation model output could be done in a shorter amount of time. One natural method to address this challenge in CoTHB could be cognitive compositionality: alternating between reasoning paths at different levels of abstraction, with high-level paths decomposing the problem into various steps, and low-level paths subsequently solving these steps. Here, neural signals associated with the value of the exploratory behavior, or with the reliabilities of alternative rules, could reflect the uncertainty associated with a particular step, and drive the creation of a dedicated low-level path to solve a specific issue. We could even imagine an algorithm integrating both branching and compositionality, which would continue the reasoning path if the reliability of the current rule is high; explore an alternative branch if the reliability of the current rule is low; and create a dedicated low-level path to reduce the uncertainty for a particular step if the reliability of the current rule is intermediate. Regardless of the specific algorithm, compositionality has already demonstrated its potential for foundation models (Zhou et al., 2023), and could be a promising approach to effectively leverage the insights of neuroimaging data for long reasoning problems. At a more fundamental level, this raises the question of whether the cognitive processes underlying human reasoning are close to an optimal computational trade-off (Koechlin, 2014), or if significantly more efficient reasoning models can be discovered. Although this remains an open question, training foundation models directly on human brain data could provide us with a starting point for experimenting on this important subject. Overall, while the specific neural signals and algorithms would likely, as for RLHB, depend on each training strategy, CoTHB could emerge as a promising method for refining the emulation of human executive function in foundation models.

6.3 Toward Brain-Trained Agents

Neural patterns from the perception level can be leveraged for aligning visual and auditory models. Neural signals from the valuation level could be particularly relevant for RLHB, and neural signals from the execution level for CoTHB. However, the case of the integration level is more intriguing. While its neural patterns can be used for aligning language models, we speculate that markers associated with conceptual integration, social cognition, and self-cognition could eventually be leveraged for the development of agents. The evolution of agentic systems is difficult to predict, but it seems reasonable to assume that future agents will be expected to collaborate more thoroughly with each other (Park et al., 2023) and with human users (Afzoon et al., 2025), in order to perform increasingly complex tasks in their environment (Wang et al., 2023). Recent research has explored cognitively inspired architectures allowing agents to generate and evaluate hypotheses about other agents (Cross et al., 2024), as well as biologically inspired architectures allowing agents to perceive and interact with real-world environments (Liu et al., 2025). The fact that neuroscience discoveries serve as a natural inspiration suggests that the incorporation of

neuroimaging data may provide valuable insights for agentic systems, opening a path toward brain-trained agents.

6.4 Toward Artificial General Intelligence

Foundation models have already reached human-level performance on a range of professional and academic benchmarks (OpenAI et al., 2024). As a result, they are increasingly seen as strong candidates for reaching AGI (Fei et al., 2022), and may even already exhibit some characteristics of AGI (Bubeck et al., 2023), at least if we consider this concept in a functional sense. From our perspective, structural AGI would imply replicating the structure of the human brain, or discovering equivalent architectures, so that an AI system could be able to acquire its own knowledge and develop cognitive abilities up to the human level. By contrast, functional AGI would simply imply replicating the functions of the human brain across a wide range of tasks, up to the level of knowledgeable individuals. While the latter objective seems more easily attainable, the current limitations of foundation models still prevent them from achieving the degree of generality and adaptability associated with human cognition (Raman et al., 2025). By leveraging brain-generated data alongside human-generated data, brain-trained foundation models could represent a realistic strategy for attenuating some of the failure modes of current AI systems in perception, valuation, execution, and integration, bringing them significantly closer to functional AGI.

6.5 Toward Artificial Superintelligence

Brain-trained foundation models may even open a path beyond functional AGI, toward functional or even structural ASI. If current foundation model architectures prove insufficient for integrating the insights of neural signals, these structural limitations could motivate the development of new architectures, more compatible with our knowledge of the human brain. Eventually, large-scale neuroimaging corpora could emerge as the ultimate benchmark for evaluating the biological plausibility, neural similarity, and cognitive alignment of foundation models, providing us with a starting point for experimenting and developing systems beyond human abilities. This strategy is perfectly compatible with the exploration of entirely new frameworks inspired by the human brain (LeCun, 2022), and in fact, it could represent a realistic and effective middle ground between continuing to scale current architectures and exploring alternative, neuroscience-inspired solutions. By starting from well-established and widely used foundation models, and progressively adapting them so that they can better accommodate the insights of neural signals, we might be able to advance toward ASI in a robust and gradual manner. Arguably, such a process would share some similarities with the evolution of the human brain itself, where all the intermediate steps had to be functional and build upon each other in a natural progression. Moreover, the same neural signals might help us ensure the alignment of ASI with human objectives, much like natural selection ensured that our brains remained aligned with the evolutionary “objectives” of survival and reproduction.

Theoretically, the promising brain regions and cognitive processes that we identified in this paper, as well as the methods we proposed, could be relevant for foundation models even if neuroimaging technologies remain at their current level. Practically, of course, this assumption is likely to be too conservative. Rather, it seems reasonable to expect that eventually, the advances in neural translation from one neuroimaging modality to another, as well as the generalization of neural interfaces, could significantly increase the quality and volume of neuroimaging data at our disposal. While RLHB and CoTHB both assume the organization of neuroimaging sessions specifically dedicated to foundation model training, a wider adoption of wearable or implantable neural technologies, for example in the context of games, could also provide us with large-scale human brain data that may be repurposed for this objective. Open-ended and complex games, in particular, could be promising targets (Mineault et al., 2025). Interestingly, neural interfaces raise

the possibility of adapting the outputs of foundation models to the neural signals of the users, searching for example for correlates of attention, curiosity, stress, fatigue, motivation, or effort at inference time, and modifying the length, complexity, or tone of the answers accordingly. Looking forward, this suggests that the interactions with foundation models could also become an opportunity for acquiring relevant neuroimaging data, monitoring the reactions of the users to specific answers, in a sort of neural feedback loop. Overall, while current foundation models have emerged from the vast corpus of human-generated data, reflecting the written and oral knowledge of humanity, brain-trained foundation models could potentially leverage a growing corpus of brain-generated data, reflecting the generative processes of human cognition that built this knowledge in the first place. There is some ambition in this strategy, which could bring us closer to combining the wisdom acquired over thousands of years by human history with the information accumulated over billions of years by biological evolution. Nevertheless, while these new horizons could provide extraordinary possibilities, they also raise important ethical, social, and technical questions, which we address in the next section.

7 CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

Classical foundation models already come with significant ethical and social challenges. Their training data can contain personal or sensitive information acquired without explicit consent for this usage, and identities can be revealed despite the anonymization efforts. The training corpus can also include social, cultural, or demographic biases, and overrepresent particular groups or ideas. Brain-trained foundation models could introduce an additional layer of complexity, considering both the highly personal and sensitive nature of human brain activity, and the comparatively smaller number of individuals for whom neuroimaging data is currently available. Therefore, these models would almost certainly require stronger informed consent procedures, along with additional protections and clarifications regarding the privacy, security, anonymity, and ownership of the data. While many of these requirements already exist for neuroimaging datasets, the acquisition of such datasets has been, until now, primarily intended for scientific or medical research, suggesting that a new evaluation of the risks should be conducted if human brain data is also leveraged for foundation model training. Critically, whereas human-generated data is the result of human intentionality and decision-making, brain-generated data can be seen as an automatic and unfiltered product of human cognition. The fact that this data precedes and could potentially predict voluntary actions highlights the necessity of implementing strong protections to ensure the freedom of thought in its most fundamental sense. We speculate that many of these questions would emerge anyway, and require adequate governance mechanisms, if neural interfaces become more widely used in the future. While these challenges are significant, they should be considered in light of the equally significant opportunities offered by brain-trained foundation models. In particular, a better alignment with human values, and a more trustworthy emulation of human executive function, could substantially improve the reliability of foundation models, expanding their human and social benefits. Furthermore, while the cost of neuroimaging data could concentrate its acquisition within economically developed regions, this equity challenge could be partially counterbalanced if grounding foundation models in the universal mechanisms of human cognition helps reduce the social, cultural, or demographic biases associated with linguistic contents.

We already mentioned some of the specific technical challenges associated with human brain data. While neuroimaging data can be noisy, distinctively individual, and difficult to interpret, methods can be developed to address these difficulties. Meanwhile, the scarcity and heterogeneity of neuroimaging datasets are increasingly mitigated by large-scale repositories and standardization, and could be further overcome by potential advances in neural translation and neural interfaces. Ultimately, the best proof

of concept for brain-trained foundation models could be the remarkable diversity of the discoveries in cognitive and computational neuroscience: if a variety of statistically significant effects can be uncovered despite the challenging nature of neuroimaging data, this suggests that many neural signals directly useful for foundation models could potentially be extracted as well. Interestingly, brain-trained foundation models could even represent a more straightforward application of neuroimaging data than many possible use cases of neural interfaces at an individual level. Indeed, whereas individual-level applications would require neural signals to be precise enough in order to deliver relevant feedback to each user, the training strategies of foundation models may more easily leverage group-level statistics, tolerating a higher threshold of variability and noise. Overall, many of the technical challenges associated with neuroimaging data reflect its singular nature: whereas human-generated data leverages a shared symbolic system, brain-generated data approximates the neural complexity of each individual, reflecting the particular ways in which each human brain processes experiences and thoughts. Since the interpretation of such neural complexity depends on the discoveries in cognitive and computational neuroscience, neuroimaging data is also fundamentally open-ended, in the sense that future discoveries could increase the value of present datasets by retroactively unlocking new neural signals of interest. Although such singularity and open-endedness strengthen the need for appropriate ethical and social measures, this evolving potential could offer significant opportunities in the long term, positioning neuroimaging data as a uniquely promising asset for the future of foundation models.

8 CONCLUSION

Foundation models have emerged as the dominant paradigm in contemporary AI. However, their reliance on observable human actions, $A(t)$, constrains them to surface-level regularities, which could partially explain some of their current limitations. In this paper, we explore a new strategy for AI: training foundation models directly on human brain data, $B^*(t)$, in order to approximate the generative processes of human brain activity, $B(t)$. We assume that neuroimaging data could give us access to a cognitive latent space that partially includes, but vastly exceeds, the narrow bandwidth of observable behavior. In other words, we hypothesize that $B^*(t)$ could include elements of $B(t)$ that are not included in $A(t)$. Alongside device-generated and human-generated data, we suggest that neuroimaging data could be distinguished as a new category, which we could call brain-generated data, in the context of foundation model training. We highlight a series of brain regions and cognitive processes whose neural signals could help overcome some of the current limitations of foundation models at the perception, valuation, execution, and integration levels. We propose two methods, RLHB and CoTHB, that could be implemented to prioritize the use of limited neuroimaging data for strategically chosen, high-value steps in foundation model training, and discuss the potential implications for agents, AGI, and ASI. We conclude by highlighting the ethical and social challenges of brain-trained foundation models, as well as the technical challenges associated with neuroimaging data, while also mentioning significant opportunities, such as a better and more universal alignment with human values. Importantly, brain-trained foundation models could represent a realistic and effective middle ground between continuing to scale current architectures and exploring alternative, neuroscience-inspired solutions. The open-ended nature of neuroimaging data, as well as the potential advances in neural translation and neural interfaces, could make this strategy increasingly relevant over time, and unlock a virtuous circle at the intersection of neuroscience and AI, as illustrated in Figure 5. For the future of foundation models, perhaps we should start building neuroimaging platforms alongside data centers.

Figure 5. Future of foundation models. *Left:* In the current strategy, classical foundation models are trained on classical training data, represented in yellow-green to emphasize the importance of observable human actions, $A(t)$. *Middle:* In the new strategy, brain-trained foundation models would incorporate neuroimaging data, $B^*(t)$, alongside classical training data. The vertical grey arrow suggests that this strategy could also motivate further advances in neuroscience, unlocking a virtuous circle. *Bottom-right:* The promising brain regions and cognitive processes identified in this paper could help overcome the current limitations of classical foundation models. *Top-right:* The horizontal grey arrow suggests potential future advances toward brain-trained agents, AGI, and ASI.

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